

EXPLORING THE OPPORTUNITIES AND OBSTACLES OF MUSHROOM CULTIVATION WITHIN AN EDUCATIONAL FRAMEWORK.

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ABSTRACT

Mushroom cultivation is a promising solution to meet the increasing food demand in India, as it can be grown on agricultural waste without requiring additional land. This study aimed to educate students about mushroom cultivation techniques, promote sustainable socio-economic development, and empower them with entrepreneurial skills. A training module was developed which included lectures on the nutritive and medicinal values of oyster mushrooms, demonstrations of bed preparation, and hands-on experience in the cultivation process. The study utilized a knowledge rating scale, performance rating scale, and attitude scale to assess the trainees' learning, performance, and change in attitudes. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data. The cultivation process involved preparing the substrate using paddy straw, spawning, incubation, and harvesting. The results indicated that the training programme enhanced the adoption and diffusion of innovations, with participants gaining knowledge, acquiring skills, and ultimately adopting and integrating the mushroom cultivation technology into their farming practices. The study highlights the potential of mushroom cultivation in creating employment opportunities, promoting sustainable development, and improving the economic standard of the masses while addressing the challenges of food security and environmental protection.

Key words:-*Mushroom Cultivation, Educational innovations, Student empowerment, Employment, Hands-on experience.*

INTRODUCTION

Addressing the food needs of a growing population with limited land resources poses a significant challenge for India's democracy, especially in this era of climate change. Mushroom farming, also known as the Non-green revolution, is an effective method to tackle this issue. Mushrooms can be cultivated on waste materials without the need for additional land, and they offer exceptional nutritional and medicinal benefits. This type of farming is cost-effective and requires intensive labor. The success of mushroom farming is largely due to its minimal input requirements. In India, the diverse climates make mushroom cultivation particularly lucrative. This technology is especially beneficial in regions where land is scarce and agricultural residues are plentiful, offering substantial employment opportunities. Additionally, mushroom farming is environmentally friendly. Much of the knowledge about mushroom cultivation originates from China, where the industry has advanced more rapidly than anywhere else in the last twenty years. Edible mushrooms have become a symbol of converting waste into protein. Through mushroom cultivation, farm waste is transformed into currency or high-value products. The technology developed for growing these edible mushrooms in controlled environments is emerging as a new way to alleviate poverty among rural populations.

PROSPECTS OF MUSHROOM CULTIVATION-The technology can be profitably considered in areas where land is limiting factor and agricultural residues are abundantly available. In India, mushroom growing can be highly rewarding because of various climates. Mushroom farming is becoming successful because of its very low inputs. Mushroom cultivation is a low cost and labour intensive activity. It can generate tremendous employment opportunities. Mushroom cultivation is eco-friendly also.

CHALLENGES OF MUSHROOMCULTIVATION-Major problems and challenges faced by the farmers were lack of knowledge in mushroom cultivation and disease management, lack of financial assistance, unavailability of High quality seeds, packaging and storing methods ,difficulties in finding proper local market and producing value added mushroom products. Along with this, availability of better and low cost substrates, approaches of maintaining hygienic conditions in the culturing sheds, effective disease controlling techniques, introduction of new varieties of edible mushroom are also essential. The research and development aspects relevant to above issues need to be promoted to have a sustainable mushroom cultivation.

SWOT ANALYSISOF MUSHROOM CULTIVATION

STRENGTH

- a. Very congenial agro-climate for year-round farming of a wide variety of mushrooms
- b. Prevalence of diverse mycophagous communities
- c. Low-cost labor, plentiful cheap supply of a wide variety of raw substrates, building materials, spawns, and other inputs
- d. The huge potential of the local market as well as easily accessible vast export market of India
- e. Mushroom venture easily adopted even by educated youths in comparison to other any agricultural ventures

WEAKNESS

- a. Lack of a critical mass of well-trained mushroom technicians and growers
- b. Lack of proper technical advice on mushroom enterprise
- c. Lack of quality control and certification
- d. Quality spawn, modernization of cultivation technology, localization of exotic technology, processing facilities
- e. Lack of well-organized market channels distribution network
- f. Inadequate scientific research on mushrooms and lack of well equipped mushroom specific laboratory/resource center and inadequate public awareness

g. Insufficient mushroom courses in School and University curriculum and inadequate coordination between public institutions providing services to the rural population

h. Poor farm management practices and marketing

OPORTUNITY

a. Rapid growth of the national and global mushroom market

b. Very suitable and important cottage industry activity in the integrated rural development program can create jobs both in semi-urban and rural areas

c. Need to increase the production and consumption of nutritious horticultural crops to ensure food & nutritional security at the household level to end the hunger and poverty by 2030

d. Growing numbers of health-conscious consumers and demand for healthy, quality and organic products

e. Highly potential for the alleviation of Protein Energy Malnutrition (PEM) and also to improve economic standard of the masses

f. Increasing interest in protection and improvement of the environment

THREAT

a. Diseases and pests damage on product quality and supply

b. The limited supply of organic pest control products.

c. Fear for a flood of Chinese mushroom and fierce competition from other neighboring countries

d. Rising input prices (including labor)

AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.The motive is to upskill and educate students and ensure a sustainable socio economic development.

2.To educate the students about the different techniques in mushroom production.

3.To strengthen the promotion of mushroom cultivation.

4.To increase the production and consumption of mushroom

5. To Empower with entrepreneurial skills

6.To uplift the community by empowering the students to effortlessly access quality education.

7. To promote recycling of Agro-wate materials and sustainable development.

8.To bridge the gap between conventional academic programs and present day methods to create a stable learning environment that has the goodness of both students and the society.

LEARNING OUTCOMES OF THE STUDY

- Classify different varieties of fungi which are commonly eaten.
- Determine the techniques used in the culture of edible mushrooms.
- Explain the production and harvesting of a mushroom crop.
- Formulate marketing strategies for mushrooms.
- Combine practical experiences with academic knowledge in our teaching methods so that learning becomes fun and effective.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

METHODOLOGY

For the present study a training module was developed .

Target Group: Students .

Training Time: October to December

Training Period: 20 days, Number of Trainees: 30 (2 batches of 15 students)

The systematic and comprehensive model of training in oyster mushroom cultivation is described. During training, monitoring was the phase for constant vigilance in ongoing training strategies.. A knowledge rating scale was developed to predict learning through training. For measuring the performance of trainees, a performance-rating scale was used. An attitude scale was used to discover the change in attitudes of trainee. Various descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyse the data. On the basis of the statistical analysis, findings were discussed and conclusions were drawn.

DESIGN OF TRAINING PROGRAMME

The design of training programme provides the structured framework and training plan.

Training objectives: The training objectives were framed on the basis of training needs of the trainees,

Curriculum development: As the need-based approach was accepted for training, the curriculum was structured on the basis of weightage given by subject expert to the objectives.

Training methodology: The training methods were selected according to objectives of curriculum.

Lecture method: Introduction to concept of mushrooms, nutritive and medicinal values of oyster mushroom were discussed in the planned lectures.

Demonstration method:-Demonstration and practical method was adopted for the bedpreparation of Oyster mushroom cultivation.

Action learning: One session of the training was for the active involvement of the trainees in the cultivation process. Each trainee prepared an oyster mushroom bed, maintained the climatic conditions and harvested the crop.

Training environment: The training environment comprises the climatic factor within training hall and interpersonal relation during training. The informal, free environment facilitates exchange of ideas and experiences.

Training Need :-Materials required are good quality Paddy Straw, Spawn (seed of mushroom) Polythene bags, Plastic string, Large vessel, Tray, Dettol, Formalin, Pottassiumpermanganate, Wood, Match box, News papers or a Polythene sheet. Mother culture of *Pleurotus florida* obtained from CARD-KVK, Thelliyoor is used for the cultivation.

DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF TRAINING PLAN

Mushroom Spawn and its preparation

The fungal mycelia of mushroom grown on suitable grains is called spawn.. It is used as inoculums to grow the mushroom. It is often called seed of the mushroom.

Preparation of the substrate-Soaking and Hot water Treatment: Paddy straw is cut into small pieces and soaked in water overnight, boiled for 30-45 minutes and excess water is drained .The water content of the straw is checked by squeezing the straw in between hands so that it contains about 75-80% moisture.

Bed preparation and Spawning-The spawned substrate in a polytene bag was called **mushroom bed**.When the sterilized substrate has cooled down to room temperature, filling and spawning was done.

Incubation and harvesting-Mushroom beds were kept either on racks in a hanging condition in the mushroom shed or mushroom house.. During spawn run the temperature should be 20-30° C , relative humidity 75-80 %,. The polythene bag is removed after 15 days..Within 4-5 days after removing the polythene bag, small pin-head like mushrooms develop. They attained maturity within two more days and harvesting was done.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

OBSERVATION AND ANALYSIS-Training courses aim at enhancing adoption and diffusion of innovations. Some of the outcomes envisaged for any training programme were gain in knowledge, gain in skill acquired and ultimately in more adoption and integration among farming community. An important indicator of the impact of training programme is the extent, to which they have adopted the package of practice of mushroom cultivation technology.

TRAINING MONITORING AND EVALUATION -Training has specific domains i.e. domain of top management, domain of trainer and domain of training. Training monitoring was the indicator of the effectiveness of organizers, trainers and the training institution.

From the 10 Mushroom beds prepared, we got about 6kg and 200 gm of good quality Oyster Mushroom .With a minimum expenditure and labour we had a good profit .It was shown in the following chart.

Training Finance---Expenditure for Mushroom Cultivation

Sl no.	Particulars	Amount in Rs:
1	Rice straw 10 bundles@Rs:20	200 for 10 beds
2	Spawn-500 gms@Rs:50	250 for 5 packets
3	Polythene bag-1 bag@Rs:10	100 for 10 bags
4	Plastic string 1bundle@Rs:15	45 for 3 bundles
5	Wood - @Rs:75/kg	300 for 4kg
6	Total expenditure	474

Target of Productivity---Income from Mushroom Cultivation

Yield in kg	Mushroom sold @rate/Kg	Income inRs:	Expenditure in Rs:	Profit in Rs:
7.100	320	2272	895	1377

The results of the training were examined for the effectiveness of the training and the impact of training on trainees. It is concluded that the development training module was effective training in the cultivation of oyster mushrooms in the tropics.

The profitability of an enterprise is a result of inter-relationship between the costs and returns. The two aspects have to be dealt separately for enhancing the net profits. In present chapter the costs and returns from mushroom cultivation have been analyzed to work out the economics of this venture. An attempt has been made to present the costs involved and pattern of output and returns. The nature of costs stems out from type and extent of inputs used and the returns from the quantum of output.

The larger education system, including general education, seems to becoming more important for raising awareness of, and distributing knowledge to, the general public. Learning is defined in experiential learning as the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience. Interactions within the learning environment allow pupils to experience the dynamics of the subject to be learnt . This hands-on activity allows the pupil to gain a personal relationship to the task through experience. That personal relationship forms the foundation and is required for understanding of the task and how it is related to its surrounding and also for the pupil's self-efficacy with respect to the activity .

Mushroom cultivation can directly improve livelihoods through economic, nutritional and medicinal contributions. Mushroom production has become an enterprise and has adopted in big way both at household level and as commercial enterprise as a source of income generation after the proper dissemination of technology through. Training courses aim at enhancing adoption and diffusion of innovations. Some of the outcomes envisaged for any training programme were gain in knowledge, gain in skill acquired and ultimately in more adoption and integration among the community. An important indicator of the impact of training programme is the extent, to which the students have adopted the package of practice of mushroom cultivation technology

Though mushroom cultivation is not so popularized in Kerala,, it comes out as an important source of livelihood for small –scale workers and farmers and can prove to be an important means to get a profitable business within a short period of time, by women self-help groups and unemployed youth. . Since mushroom grows on various locally available substrates and their cultivation is of short duration and involves a simple and low-cost technology, there are good prospects for their commercial cultivation in Kerala.

CONCLUSION

India is primarily an agriculture-based country. The diversity in soil and climatic conditions allows a production of variety of crops in different parts of the country. This provides vast potential for the cultivation of mushrooms due to ample availability of raw materials and conducive climatic conditions. Mushroom cultivation is becoming popular because it is not only meets the dietary requirements but also adds to the economic development of growers with insufficient land. Mushroom cultivation technology can be profitably considered in areas where land is a limiting factor and agricultural residues are abundantly available. Cultivation of mushroom has various advantages as it converts complex organic ligno-cellulosic compounds into nutritious food, aids recycling of agro-waste, contributes to pollution control, does not compete with agricultural land and provides avenues to self employment. The study revealed that exposure to training had increased the knowledge of students, and youths regarding techniques of mushroom production. The reason behind the satisfactory change in perception level might be due to well educational background, keen interest of participants and methods followed for technology transfer to the trainees. The study revealed that the mushroom production training has created a favourable attitude among the trainees(students) and also enhanced the economic level of beneficiaries who adopted it as a source of livelihood. Mushroom cultivation can prove to be an important means to get a profitable business with in a short period of time. Hence there is an urgent need to popularize the technology amongst the community.

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